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Epidemiology and Risk Factors of Sports Injuries in Indian Elite University Wrestlers - A Retrospective Study

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Abstract

Background: Wrestling is a strength dominated and collision-based sport played at the different level of competitions in India. Wrestling is a highest injury prone sport of all individual sports.

Purpose: To identify the frequency, incidence, severity and risk factor associated with the injuries occurring in Indian Elite wrestler.

Design: Descriptive epidemiology study.

Methods: The present study was a retrospective study on Elite Wrestlers from All India Inter-University Wrestling Competition during Nov, 2017. Researcher collected daily training and match-play injury data through a well-structured injury report form. The injury report form consists of common injuries, anatomical body location, injury severity and risk factors (reason of injury). The risk factors include two dimensions one is intrinsic and second one is extrinsic risk factors. The severity of the injury based on the amount of time lost from training and competition due to sports injuries.

Results: the incidence rate (IR) for all India University Wrestling Championship was 67.07 per 1000 hours, epidemiologic incidence proportion (IP) was 0.125 and clinical incidence was 0.412. The mean of injury severity was 81.05 days lost from training and competition.

Conclusion: It was observed that fracture is a highest frequent injury with 9.14 incidence rate (IR) followed by contusion with 7.11 IR. Most severe injury in wrestling assigned ranked one is also fracture with 445 days lost from training and competition followed by ligament rupture with 180 days lost from training and competition.

Key Words: Sports injury, wrestling, epidemiology, retrospective.

1. Introduction:

The wrestling is a popular sport in many countries of the world. Its origin dates back to the Sumerians as early as 5000 BC. The two fighting styles internationally recognized are; Greco-Roman (GR), which made its debut in the first modern Olympic Games in Athens (1896) and Freestyle which was included in the Saint Louis Olympic program (1904). Like all sports, the wrestling is beneficial for its participants and has been linked to better grades, lower school absences and better behavior. However, the arduous nature of sport has led to reporting injury rates of up to 30.7 injuries per 1000 exposed athletes among wrestlers, surpassed only by injury rates among college football players.

Wrestling is a combat sport involving grappling type techniques such as clinch fighting, throws and takedowns, joint locks, pins and other grappling holds. The sport can either be theatrical for entertainment, or genuinely competitive. A wrestling bout is a physical competition, between two (occasionally more) competitors or sparring partners, who attempt to gain and maintain a superior position. There are a wide range of styles with varying rules with both traditional historic and modern styles. Wrestling techniques have been incorporated into other martial arts as well as military hand-to-hand combat system.

2. Research Process and Methodology:

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the injury profile as well as recognized the risk factors associated with the injuries in Elite Indian Wrestler during All Indian Inter University Championship held at Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak.

2.1 Research Design:

The present study was a retrospective study on Elite Wrestlers from All India Inter-University Wrestling Competition during Nov, 2017 in Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak. The data of injury has been collected during competitions within a certain period of time.

2.2 Selection of the Sample:

The present study was delimited to the wrestlers of Indian Universities only. So, the players participated in the All India Inter University Wrestling Championship was selected as sample. The participation level of the all samples were same. The age of selected sample were ranged from 18 to 25.

2.3 Selection of the Variables:

In the area of sports injuries selection of the variables is a very important aspect. Researcher collected daily training and match-play injury data through a well-structured injury report form. The injury report form consists of common injuries, anatomical body location, injury severity and risk factors (reason of injury). The risk factors include two dimensions one is intrinsic and second one is extrinsic risk factors. The severity of the injury based on the amount of time lost from training and competition due to sports injuries. Injury incidence rate, epidemiologic incidence proportion (IP) and clinical incidence rate was also assessed. Measures of incidence in sports injury epidemiology should always be accompanied by confidence intervals (CIs). The standard interpretation of the 95% CI is as follows: If a given study were hypothetically repeated 100 times and 100 CIs were computed from those studies, 95 of the 100 CIs would contain the true incidence in the population. Confidence intervals are related to study size. A small study generally has wide CIs, indicating a less precise study, whereas a larger study has narrower CIs (better precision). Of course, the underlying variability of the rate also affects the CI.

Confidence intervals are closely related to P values. For example, suppose a researcher wanted to test whether the injury rate was different in 2 sports. This could be done by using a P value or, equivalently, by comparing the 95% CIs for the rates. If the 95% CIs do not overlap, then (in general) the P value for testing whether the rates are different will be statistically significant at the 5% level.

Confidence intervals are more useful than P values because they contain more information than do P values alone. A P value is just one number, whereas a CI is a range. Put another way, CIs separate the size of the study (the width of the interval) from the size of the effect (the rate), whereas P values combine the study size and the study effect into 1 overall measure.

Injury Definitions:

An injury was defined as “an injury preventing a players from talking full part in training or match-play for a period of greater than 24 hours from midnight at the end of the day the injury was sustained”. Injury severity was reported as “the number of days that had elapsed between the day the injury was sustained until the player returns to full training and availability for match-play selection”. A recurrent injury was defined as “an injury of the same type and at the same site as an index injury and which occurs after a player’s return to full participation from the index injury”. Training exposure was defined as “team-based and individual physical activities under the control or guidance of the team’s coaching and fitness staff that are aimed at maintaining or improving player’s wrestling skills or physical conditioning”.

2.3 Statistical Technique:

Incidence refers to the number of new occurrences of injuries during a specified period of time. Risk and rates are two separate ways of measuring the incidence of sport injury, but many people incorrectly assume that rates and risks are essentially one and the same. In this study 3 measures of incidence were used—epidemiologic incidence proportion (IP), incidence rate (IR), and clinical incidence respectively. The epidemiologic IP is interpreted as the average risk of injury per athlete and the IR is the incidence of injury per unit of athlete time, whereas the clinical incidence is more appropriate as measures of resource utilization. The incidence rate is expressed as rate per 1000 players exposures with 95% confidence interval and injury severity is expressed as mean numbers of days lost with 95% of confidence interval. (See table no. 1)

Table -1 Calculation of incidence measures

Incidence Measures	Estimated Incidence	Formula for SE	95% Confidence Interval
Incidence Rate (IR)	Total injury/athlete-exposure ×1000	$\frac{\sqrt{\text{total injuries}}}{\sum \text{athlete exposures}}$	IR per athlete ± 1.96 SE)×1000
Epidemiologic Incidence proportion (IP)	Injured athlete/total athlete	$\frac{\sqrt{IP \times (1 - IP)}}{n}$	IP per athlete ± 1.96 SE
Clinical Incidence	Injuries/total athletes	Same as for epidemiologic IP	CI per athlete ± 1.96 SE

The numbers of injuries are reported for the duration of the championship, and injury incidence is reported per 1000 player hours. The All India Inter University Wrestling championship consisted of a total 123 bouts for 16 team of AIIU, MDU Rohtak. The 123 matches involved 61.5 player hours. Players hours were calculated as follow 123 matches × 0.05 hours per match = 6.15 total match hours × 160 players = 984 player hours.

3. Results of the Study:

The table 4.1 shows the subject’s characteristics of the selected samples. The mean and standard deviation of the respondents was 20.6±1.87, mean and SD of height was 174.8±12.33, mean and SD of the weight of respondents was 80.40±17.30 and the mean and SD of the experience was 5.55±2.48 respectively.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-2 Subject Characteristics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	SE	Minimum	Maximum
AGE	20	20.6000	1.87504	.419	18	27
HEIGHT	20	174.8100	12.33959	2.75	142.50	195.60
WEIGHT	20	80.4000	17.30348	3.86	59	130
EXPERIENCE	20	5.5500	2.48098	.554	2	10

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-3 Distribution of injury incidences in Wrestling

	Estimated incidence	SE	95 % Confidence Interval
Incidence Rate (IR)	67.07	0.008	(44.32,75.68)
Epidemiology Incidence Proportion (IP)	0.125	0.731	(1.30,1.43)
Clinical Incidence	0.412	0.242	(0.06,0.88)

“Incidence reported per 1000 hours.

Table 4.2 reveals that incidence rate of wrestler was 67.07 per 1000 hours and 95% confidence interval (CI) was 44.32±75.68. Epidemiologic incidence proportion (IP) was 0.125 and 95% confidence interval was 1.30±1.43; clinical incidence was 0.412 injury per athlete CI was 0.06±0.88 respectively.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-4 Distribution of severity and incidence of injuries and ranking as per time lost in days

Injuries	N	%	IR	Severity	Rank*
Abrasion	4	6.1	4.065	3	13
Contusion	7	10.60	7.11	13	10
Incision	7	10.60	7.11	23	9
dislocation	6	9.09	6.09	165	3
Fracture	9	13.63	9.14	445	1
Jerk	5	7.54	5.08	31	7
Ligament rupture	4	6.1	4.06	180	2
Inflammation	1	1.5	1.01	70	5
Muscle cramp	2	3.03	2.03	3	13
Muscle pull	4	6.1	4.065	26	8
Pain	5	7.54	5.08	12	11
sprain	7	10.60	7.11	100	4
Strain	2	3.03	2.03	3	13
wound	3	4.54	3.04	67	6

*Incidence reported per 1000 hours; severity reported as time lost in days.

*1st rank given to the largest value.

Table 4.3 explores the distribution of severity and incidence of injuries and ranking as per time lost in days. Fracture assigned 1st rank of severity with 445 days lost from training and competition follow by ligament rupture with 180 days and third most severe injury was dislocation with 165 days lost from training and competition. But the incidence rate (IR) was different from severity. The risk of fracture is highest in wrestling with 9.14 IR and highest severity but contusion is follow by 7.11 IR and their severity assigned 10th rank.

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..1 injury incidence (per 1000 hours) and injury severity as per time lost in days from competition and training

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-5 Distribution of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Causes

S. No	Intrinsic Cause	N	N*	Fr. (%)	IR	Extrinsic Cause	N	N*	Fr. (%)	IR
1	Diet	19	21	-		Bare foot	19	25	-	
2	Fatigue	19	21	-		Carelessness	19	25	-	
3	Fitness	19	21	4 (19.04)	4.06	Climatic condition	19	25	1(4)	1.01
4	Improper training	19	21	-		Collision	19	25	11(44)	11.17
5	Improper warming up	19	21	1 (4.76)	1.01	Competition	19	25	2(8)	2.03
6	Jerk	19	21	2(9.52)	2.03	Drugs	19	25	-	
7	Mentally disturb	19	21	-		Fall or slip	19	25	4(16)	4.06
8	Over loading	19	21	2(9.52)	2.03	Faulty equipment	19	25	-	
9	Over stretching	19	21	3(14.28)	3.04	Field/playground	19	25	2(8)	2.03
10	Over training	19	21	-		Grip	19	25	1(4)	1.01
11	Twist	19	21	8(38.09)	8.13	Poor technique	19	25	-	
12	Unknown	19	21	1(4.76)	1.01	Unknown	19	25	4(16)	4.06

N=Total number of sample; N* = total no of multiple responses

Table no. 4.4 shows the distribution of intrinsic and extrinsic causes and their incidence rate. It was observed that twisting in intrinsic causes has height incidence rate per 1000 player hours with 38.09% out of 21 responses followed by fitness with 4.06 incidence rate (IR) and percentage distribution was 19.04 and 3rd most prone injury reason was over stretching (IR) 3.04 with 14.28% respectively. In extrinsic causes collision was more injury prone with incidence rate (IR) of 11.17 and 44% followed by fall or slip with (IR) 4.06 and 16% and 3rd most prone reason was field and playground with 2.03 incidence rate (IR) and 8% respectively.

4. Conclusions:

The present study highlights that incidence rate of wrestler during competition was 67.07 per 1000 player hours. It means there is risk of 67 injuries occurrence in 1000 hours in wrestling. Whereas, incidence proportion was 0.125 or 12.5% indicate that average risk was 12 player injured during competition and clinical incidence was 0.412 injuries per athlete during all India University Wrestling Championship. It was observed that fracture is a highest frequent injury with 9.14 incidence rate (IR) followed by contusion with 7.11 IR. Most severe injury in wrestling assigned ranked one is also fracture with 445 days lost from training and competition followed by ligament rupture with 180 days lost from training and competition.

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